

Low-complexity Ordered Statistic Decoder for Primitive Rateless Codes

Mahyar Shirvanimoghaddam, Ming Xiao, Mikael Skoglund

Abstract—We investigate the performance of primitive rateless (PR) codes and introduce an enhanced ordered statistics decoder (OSD) designed for decoding them. We demonstrate that constructing PR codes using linear Boolean functions simplifies decoding to identifying dual bases over $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$. By leveraging self-dual bases over $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$, the decoding process for high-rate PR codes is simplified, contributing to a reduced complexity OSD algorithm. Through simulations, we establish that high-rate PR codes can achieve block error rates comparable to their BCH counterparts across various signal-to-noise ratios (SNRs) and code rates. The PR code can be tailored to any rate and block length, and the proposed OSD algorithm makes it well-suited for low-latency applications.

Index Terms—Finite field, linear-feedback shift-register, rate-compatible codes, ordered statistics decoder.

I. INTRODUCTION

In ultra-reliable low-latency communications (URLLC), meeting strict latency and reliability demands relies on short block-length codes with robust error-correction capabilities [1]. Various candidates, including extended Bose, Chaudhuri, and Hocquenghem (eBCH) codes, cyclic-redundancy-check-aided polar (CRC-Polar) codes, and polarization-adjusted convolutional (PAC) codes, have demonstrated the capacity to approach the normal approximation (NA) bound across various block lengths and signal-to-noise ratios (SNRs).

Meeting the latency requirements of URLLC applications necessitates the use of low-complexity decoders alongside high-performance channel codes. While CRC-Polar codes can achieve near maximum likelihood (ML) performance with the successive cancellation list (SCL) decoding algorithm [2], the decoder entails a large list size and successive operations, resulting in elevated latency. Additionally, URLLC demands bit-level granularity for block lengths and coding rates to adapt to scenarios with diverse latency and bandwidth constraints [1]. Recently introduced as potential universal decoders for URLLC, advanced Ordered-Statistics Decoding (OSD) [3], [4] and Guessing Random Additive Noise Decoding (GRAND) [5], [6] offer the capability to decode any linear block code. These decoders enable the consideration of well-established linear codes with flexible block lengths and rates for URLLC applications.

Primitive Rateless (PR) codes were recently proposed in [7] and can be designed for any blocklength and rate, and were shown to meet the Gilbert-Varshamov bound for any rates

The paper was accepted and presented at IEEE International Communications Conference (ICC), Montreal, Canada, June 2025.

The work was supported by European Commission, Horizon Europe MSCA Project, Flexible Channel Coding for 6G Short Packet Communication (Grant ID. 101062049).

The authors are with the Division of Information Science and Engineering, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm, Sweden (emails: {mshirvan, mingx, skoglund}@kth.se).

below 0.5. While exhibiting a marginally reduced minimum Hamming weight in contrast to BCH codes, PR codes achieve comparable block error rate (BLER) performance, attributed largely to their lower number of low-weight codewords [7]. These qualities, coupled with their exceptionally simple encoding algorithm, position PR codes as promising contenders for URLLC applications. PR codes can be decoded using universal decoders such as OSD [3], [4] or its variants, which offer lower complexities in terms of the number of test error patterns (TEPs).

In this paper, we present the Boolean function construction of PR codes and demonstrate that decoding can be simplified to identifying the dual basis of a given basis over $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$, involving matrix inversion over $\mathbf{GF}(2)$. By utilizing self-dual bases for constructing a high-rate PR code with message length k and codeword length n with $n-k \leq k$, the decoding process is further simplified, involving the inversion of a $t \times t$ binary matrix with a complexity of $\mathcal{O}(t^3)$ binary operations, where $0 \leq t \leq n-k$, in comparison with the conventional OSD algorithm, which requires $\mathcal{O}(n(n-k)^2)$ operations [8] for the Gaussian elimination. Simulation results reveal that high-rate PR codes can achieve BLERs comparable to BCH counterparts across various signal-to-noise ratios (SNRs) and code rates when decoded with the proposed low-complexity decoder. Unlike BCH codes, PR codes can be easily designed at any rate and blocklength by selecting a suitable primitive polynomial. Furthermore, we compare the modified OSD decoder with soft guessing random additive noise decoder (SGRAND) [5] and ordered-reliability bits GRAND (ORBGRAND) [6], and show that high-rate PR codes decoded with the OSD decoder require significantly fewer test error patterns (TEPs) or codebook queries.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II provides a background review, Section III presents the Boolean function construction of PR codes, Section IV introduces a modified OSD decoder for high-rate PR codes along with simulation results, and Section V concludes the paper.

II. PRELIMINARIES

A. Primitive Rateless Code

A primitive rateless (PR) code [7], denoted by $\text{PR}(k, p(x))$, is characterized by the information block length k and a binary primitive polynomial $p(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} p_i x^i$ of degree k , for $p_0 = p_k = 1$, which is the minimal polynomial of a primitive element α over $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$. A generator matrix of a PR code $\text{PR}(k, p(x))$ truncated at length n , which is denoted by $\text{PR}(k, n, p(x))$, is constructed as follows:

$$\mathbf{G}_n = [\mathbf{g}_0, \mathbf{g}_1, \dots, \mathbf{g}_{n-1}], \quad (1)$$

where the i^{th} column, i.e., \mathbf{g}_i is the binary representation of α^{i-1} , for $1 \leq i \leq n$. Since α is a primitive element of $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$, $\{0, 1, \alpha, \alpha^2, \dots, \alpha^{2^k-2}\}$ is the entire field $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$ [9]. A parity check matrix of $\text{PR}(k, n, p(x))$ is given by [7]:

$$\mathbf{H}_n = \begin{bmatrix} p_0 & p_1 & \cdots & p_k & 0 & 0 & \cdots \\ 0 & p_0 & p_1 & \cdots & p_k & 0 & \cdots \\ & \ddots & & \ddots & & \ddots & \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & p_0 & p_1 & \cdots & p_k \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

The encoding of PR codes can be simply implemented using a linear feedback shift register (LFSR) with the connection polynomial $x^k p(1/x)$ and the initial states equal to the information sequence (Fig. 1). In fact, each codeword \mathbf{c} of a PR code satisfies the linear recurrence equation $\sum_{i=0}^k p_i c_{i+j-k} = 0$ for any $j \geq k$.

A PR code $\text{PR}(k, n, p(x))$ can be also realized as a punctured Simplex code [7, Remark 2]. Also, as shown in [7, Lemma 2], there are $\frac{\varphi(2^k-1)}{k}$ PR codes of message length k , where $\varphi(\cdot)$ is the Euler's totient function. Furthermore, any PR code $\text{PR}(k, n, p(x))$ is the dual of a polynomial code of codeword length n , message length $n - k$, and generator polynomial $p(x)$ [7, Remark 4].

B. Boolean Functions and Bases over $\mathbf{GF}(2)$

We recall that the trace function $\text{Tr} : \mathbf{GF}(2^k) \rightarrow \mathbf{GF}(2)$ is a linear mapping from $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$ to $\mathbf{GF}(2)$, defined as $\text{Tr}(z) = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} z^{2^i}$ for any $z \in \mathbf{GF}(2^k)$. Any linear mapping (Boolean function) $f : \mathbf{GF}(2^k) \rightarrow \mathbf{GF}(2)$ can be represented in the form $f(z) = \text{Tr}(\beta z)$ for some $\beta \in \mathbf{GF}(2^k)$, for any $z \in \mathbf{GF}(2^k)$ [9]. Accordingly, there are 2^k linear Boolean functions f [10].

The set of k elements $\{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1} := \{\alpha_0, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_{k-1}\}$ from $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$ form a basis of $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$ over $\mathbf{GF}(2)$, if and only if every element $z \in \mathbf{GF}(2^k)$ can be represented in the form $z = \sum_{i=1}^k z_i \alpha_i$, where $z_i \in \mathbf{GF}(2)$. Let $\{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1} = \{\alpha_0, \dots, \alpha_{k-1}\}$ and $\{\beta_i\}_0^{k-1} = \{\beta_0, \dots, \beta_{k-1}\}$ be bases for $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$, f a linear Boolean function, and $\gamma \in \mathbf{GF}(2^k)$, $\gamma \neq 0$. Then, the bases are said to be dual with respect to f and γ , if for all $0 \leq i, j \leq k-1$, $f(\gamma \alpha_i \beta_j) = \delta_{i,j}$, where $\delta_{i,j}$ is 1 if $i = j$, and is 0 otherwise. As shown in [10, Theorem 3], any $z \in \mathbf{GF}(2^k)$ can be represented in the dual basis as follows:

$$z = \sum_{i=1}^k f(\gamma z \alpha_i) \beta_i. \quad (3)$$

It was shown in [10, Theorem 2], that every basis has a unique dual basis with respect to any nonzero linear Boolean function f and any nonzero $\gamma \in \mathbf{GF}(2^k)$. A basis $\{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1}$ is called self-dual with respect to f , if and only if $f(\alpha_i \alpha_j) = \delta_{i,j}$. As shown in [11], $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$ has a self-dual basis over $\mathbf{GF}(2)$ with respect to the trace function. The number $sd(k, 2)$ of self-dual bases of $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$ over $\mathbf{GF}(2)$ with respect to the trace function is given by $sd(k, 2) = \frac{1}{k!} \prod_{i=1}^{k-1} (2^i - a_i)$, where $a_i \equiv (i+1) \pmod{2}$ [11].

Fig. 1. The encoding circuit of the PR code $\text{PR}(k, p(x))$ using a LFSR with connection polynomial $x^k p(1/x)$ and initial state $[b_{k-1}, \dots, b_1, b_0]$.

III. CONSTRUCTION OF PR CODES USING BOOLEAN FUNCTIONS

In this section, we represent PR codes using Boolean functions.

Lemma 1 (Boolean function construction of PR codes). *Let $p(x) = \sum_{i=0}^k p_i x^i$ with $p_0 = p_k = 1$ denote the minimal polynomial of a primitive element α over $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$. Let $\{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1}$ denote a basis of $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$ with respect to the linear Boolean function f , and $\{\gamma_i\}_0^{k-1}$ be its dual basis. We construct a code, denoted by $\text{PR}(k, p(x), \{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1})$, such that for any information block $[b_0, b_1, \dots, b_{k-1}]$, the i^{th} coded symbol is $c_i = f(\mathbf{b}\beta_i)$, where $\mathbf{b} = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} b_i \gamma_i$ and*

$$\beta_i = \begin{cases} \alpha_i, & \text{if } 0 \leq i \leq k-1, \\ \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} p_j \beta_{i+j-k}, & \text{if } i \geq k. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The code $\text{PR}(k, p(x), \{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1})$ is equivalent to the PR code $\text{PR}(k, p(x))$.

Proof: It is easy to show that for $j \geq k$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} p_i c_{i+j-k} &= \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} p_i f(\mathbf{b}\beta_{i+j-k}) = f\left(\mathbf{b} \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} p_i \beta_{i+j-k}\right) \\ &\stackrel{(a)}{=} f(\mathbf{b}\beta_j) = c_j, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where step (a) follows from (4). It is then clear that a parity check matrix of this code is (2). This completes the proof. ■

Proposition 1. *For β_j 's satisfying equation (4), the following holds:*

$$[\beta_0, \dots, \beta_{n-1}] = [\alpha_0, \dots, \alpha_{k-1}] \mathbf{G}_n, \quad (6)$$

where the i^{th} column of \mathbf{G}_n , is the binary representation of α^{i-1} , for $1 \leq i \leq n$, as in (1).

Proof: This can be easily shown as the β_j 's satisfy the linear recurrence equation (4), characterized by the primitive polynomial $p(x)$ with root α . ■

Proposition 2. *The encoder of the PR code $\text{PR}(k, p(x), \{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1})$ defined in Lemma 1, where $\{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1}$ and $\{\gamma_i\}_0^{k-1}$ are dual bases of $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$ with respect to the linear Boolean function f , i.e., $f(\alpha_i \gamma_j) = \delta_{i,j}$, is systematic, and its generator matrix truncated at length n , is given by \mathbf{G}_n as in (1), where the i^{th} column is the binary representation of α^{i-1} .*

Proof: Using Lemma 1 and the definition of β_i in (4), for any information block $[b_0, b_1, \dots, b_{k-1}]$, where $\mathbf{b} = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} b_i \gamma_i$, the j^{th} coded symbol is obtained as follows for

$0 \leq j \leq k-1$:

$$c_j = f(\mathbf{b}\beta_j) = f\left(\alpha_j \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} b_i \gamma_i\right) = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} b_i f(\gamma_i \alpha_j) \stackrel{(a)}{=} b_j,$$

where step (a) follows from $f(\gamma_i \alpha_j) = \delta_{i,j}$. Therefore, the encoder of PR $(k, p(x), \{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1})$ is systematic. Since PR $(k, p(x), \{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1})$ and PR $(k, p(x))$ are the same, and their encoders are systematic, their generator matrix is also the same. This completes the proof. \blacksquare

The information block $[b_0, \dots, b_{k-1}]$ can be recovered from any set of k coded symbols $\{c_{i_0}, c_{i_1}, \dots, c_{i_{k-1}}\}$, where their corresponding columns of \mathbf{G}_n , denoted by $\mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{B}} = [\mathbf{g}_{i_0}, \dots, \mathbf{g}_{i_{k-1}}]$ are linearly independent. In other words, one can recover \mathbf{b} from $[c_{i_0}, c_{i_1}, \dots, c_{i_{k-1}}]$ if $\{\beta_{i_j}\}_{j=0}^{k-1}$ is a basis of $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$ with respect to function f , where β_{i_j} is defined in (4) for $0 \leq j \leq k-1$. Let $\{\mu_j\}_{j=0}^{k-1}$ denote the dual basis of $\{\beta_{i_j}\}_{j=0}^{k-1}$ with respect to function f . We are interested in finding the $k \times k$ binary matrix \mathbf{L} such that $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{M}$, where $\mathbf{B} = [\beta_{i_0}, \dots, \beta_{i_{k-1}}]^\top$, $\mathbf{M} = [\mu_0, \dots, \mu_{k-1}]^\top$, and $^\top$ is the matrix transpose operator. By multiplying both sides of $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{M}$ by \mathbf{B}^\top , we have $\mathbf{B}\mathbf{B}^\top = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{M}\mathbf{B}^\top$. By applying function f to both sides of this equation, we get

$$f(\mathbf{B}\mathbf{B}^\top) = \mathbf{L}f(\mathbf{M}\mathbf{B}^\top), \quad (7)$$

where $f(\mathbf{M}\mathbf{B}^\top) = \mathbf{I}_k$. This is because the element in the ℓ th row and j th column of $f(\mathbf{M}\mathbf{B}^\top)$ is $f(\mu_\ell \beta_{i_j})$ and since $\{\mu_j\}_{j=0}^{k-1}$ and $\{\beta_{i_j}\}_{j=0}^{k-1}$ are dual bases with respect to function f , we have $f(\mu_\ell \beta_{i_j}) = \delta_{\ell,j}$. Therefore, (7) can be simplified to

$$\mathbf{L} = f(\mathbf{B}\mathbf{B}^\top) = \begin{bmatrix} f(\beta_{i_0}\beta_{i_0}) & \cdots & f(\beta_{i_0}\beta_{i_{k-1}}) \\ f(\beta_{i_1}\beta_{i_0}) & \cdots & f(\beta_{i_1}\beta_{i_{k-1}}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ f(\beta_{i_{k-1}}\beta_{i_0}) & \cdots & f(\beta_{i_{k-1}}\beta_{i_{k-1}}) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

The dual basis \mathbf{M} can then be calculated by $\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{L}^{-1}\mathbf{B}$. We can further represent \mathbf{M} in terms of basis $\{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1}$ as follows:

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{L}^{-1}\mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{B}}^\top \mathbf{A}, \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{A} = [\alpha_0, \dots, \alpha_{k-1}]^\top$ and $\mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{B}} = [\mathbf{g}_{i_0}, \dots, \mathbf{g}_{i_{k-1}}]$. Since each element of $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$ can be represented in terms of basis $\{\beta_{i_j}\}_{j=0}^{k-1}$ using (3), each coded symbol c_j can be found as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} c_j &= f(\mathbf{b}\beta_j) = f\left(\mathbf{b} \sum_{\ell=0}^{k-1} f(\beta_j \mu_\ell) \beta_{i_\ell}\right) \\ &= \sum_{\ell=0}^{k-1} f(\beta_j \mu_\ell) f(\mathbf{b}\beta_{i_\ell}) = \sum_{\ell=0}^{k-1} f(\beta_j \mu_\ell) c_{i_\ell}. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Using (9) and the fact that $\beta_i = \alpha_i$ for $0 \leq i \leq k-1$, we can easily show that the codeword \mathbf{c} corresponding to information block $[b_0, \dots, b_{k-1}]$, can be uniquely found from $\mathbf{c}_{\mathbf{B}} = [c_{i_0}, c_{i_1}, \dots, c_{i_{k-1}}]$, as follows:

$$\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{c}_{\mathbf{B}} \mathbf{L}^{-1} \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{B}}^\top \mathbf{F}, \quad (11)$$

where

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} f(\beta_0\beta_0) & \cdots & f(\beta_0\beta_{n-1}) \\ f(\beta_1\beta_0) & \cdots & f(\beta_1\beta_{n-1}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ f(\beta_{k-1}\beta_0) & \cdots & f(\beta_{k-1}\beta_{n-1}) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

A. PR Codes Constructed using Self-Dual Bases

We now consider a PR code PR $(k, p(x), \{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1})$, where $\{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1}$ is a self-dual basis of $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$ with respect to the linear Boolean function f . As mentioned previously, the information sequence $\mathbf{b} = [b_0, \dots, b_{k-1}]$ can be recovered from any set of k coded symbols $\{c_{i_0}, c_{i_1}, \dots, c_{i_{k-1}}\}$, if $\{\beta_{i_j}\}_{j=0}^{k-1}$ is a basis of $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$ with respect to function f . Without loss of generality, we assume that $0 \leq i_0 < i_1 < \dots < i_{k-1} \leq n-1$ and $t = \arg \max_j \{j | i_{k-j} \geq k\}$. Since $\{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1}$ is a self-dual basis and $\beta_i = \alpha_i$ for $i = 0, 1, \dots, k-1$ according to (4), we have $f(\beta_{i_\ell} \beta_{i_j}) = \delta_{\ell,j}$ for $0 \leq \ell, j \leq k-t-1$. Therefore, matrix \mathbf{L} in (8) can be rewritten as follows:

$$\mathbf{L} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{k-t} & \mathbf{D} \\ \mathbf{D}^\top & \mathbf{S} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{I}_{k-t} is the $(k-t) \times (k-t)$ identity matrix, and \mathbf{D} and \mathbf{S} are respectively given by:

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} f(\beta_{i_0}\beta_{i_{k-t}}) & \cdots & f(\beta_{i_0}\beta_{i_{k-1}}) \\ \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ f(\beta_{i_{k-t-1}}\beta_{i_{k-t}}) & \cdots & f(\beta_{i_{k-t-1}}\beta_{i_{k-1}}) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{S} = \begin{bmatrix} f(\beta_{i_{k-t}}^2) & \cdots & f(\beta_{i_{k-t}}\beta_{i_{k-1}}) \\ \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ f(\beta_{i_{k-1}}\beta_{i_{k-t}}) & \cdots & f(\beta_{i_{k-1}}^2) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (15)$$

Using (6), we have $[\beta_{i_0}, \dots, \beta_{i_{k-t-1}}] = \mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{D}}$ and $[\beta_{i_{k-t}}, \dots, \beta_{i_{k-1}}] = \mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{S}}$, where $\mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{D}} = [\mathbf{g}_{i_0}, \dots, \mathbf{g}_{i_{k-t-1}}]$ and $\mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{S}} = [\mathbf{g}_{i_{k-t}}, \dots, \mathbf{g}_{i_{k-1}}]$. Since $f(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{A}^\top) = \mathbf{I}_k$ and that f is linear, we can easily find matrices \mathbf{D} and \mathbf{S} as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{D} &= f(\mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{D}}^\top \mathbf{A}\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{S}}) = \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{D}}^\top f(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{A}^\top) \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{S}} = \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{D}}^\top \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{S}}, \\ \mathbf{S} &= f(\mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{S}}^\top \mathbf{A}\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{S}}) = \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{S}}^\top f(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{A}^\top) \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{S}} = \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{S}}^\top \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{S}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 3. For a PR code PR $(k, p(x), \{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1})$, where $\{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1}$ is a self-dual basis of $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$ with respect to the linear Boolean function f , the codeword associated with the information block $[b_0, \dots, b_{k-1}]$ can be found from $\mathbf{c}_{\mathbf{B}} = [c_{i_0}, c_{i_1}, \dots, c_{i_{k-1}}]$, where $\{\beta_{i_j}\}_{j=0}^{k-1}$ is a basis of $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$ with respect to function f , as follows:

$$\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{c}_{\mathbf{B}} \mathbf{L}^{-1} \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{B}}^\top \mathbf{G}. \quad (16)$$

Proof: Using (4) and (11) and the fact that $\{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1}$ is a self-dual basis of $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$ with respect to f , we have $f(\beta_j \beta_\ell) = \delta_{j,\ell}$, for $0 \leq \ell, j \leq k-1$. Therefore, the sub-matrix containing the first k columns of \mathbf{F} in (12) is the identity matrix. Since the encoder of PR $(k, p(x), \{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1})$ is systematic (Proposition 2), we will have

$$[b_0, \dots, b_{k-1}] = \mathbf{c}_{\mathbf{B}} \mathbf{L}^{-1} \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{B}}^\top, \quad (17)$$

and the rest of the codeword can be easily found by multiplying $[b_0, \dots, b_{k-1}]$ with \mathbf{G} . This completes the proof. \blacksquare

IV. THE PERFORMANCE OF HIGH-RATE PR CODES USING A MODIFIED OSD ALGORITHM

For the PR code $\text{PR}(k, p(x), \{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1})$, where $\{\alpha_i\}_0^{k-1}$ is a self-dual basis of $\mathbf{GF}(2^k)$ with respect to function f , the inverse of matrix \mathbf{L} in (13) is given by:

$$\mathbf{L}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{k-t} + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{L}_s^{-1}\mathbf{D}^\top & \mathbf{D}\mathbf{L}_s^{-1} \\ \mathbf{L}_s^{-1}\mathbf{D}^\top & \mathbf{L}_s^{-1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (18)$$

where $\mathbf{L}_s = \mathbf{S} + \mathbf{D}^\top\mathbf{D}$. This means that inverting matrix \mathbf{L} of size $k \times k$ involves inverting a smaller matrix \mathbf{L}_s of size $t \times t$ and some matrix operations. It is important to note that inverting matrix \mathbf{L} in (13) can be efficiently performed by using Gaussian elimination and row-wise operations, similar to the inactivation decoding of LT and Raptor codes proposed in [12]. In particular, we first zero out the submatrix \mathbf{D}^\top by row-wise operations. This is equivalent to multiplying \mathbf{D}^\top by the submatrix $[\mathbf{I}_t \ \mathbf{D}]$ and adding it to the last t rows of matrix \mathbf{L} . We then perform Gaussian elimination with complexity $\mathcal{O}(t^3)$ [8] to find the inverse of $\mathbf{S} + \mathbf{D}^\top\mathbf{D}$. The next step is to zero out sub-matrix \mathbf{D} by row-wise operations. For moderate to high-rate codes, when $R > 0.5$, it is easy to show that $0 \leq t \leq k(R^{-1} - 1)$; that is when R is large, then t can be very small. The proposed decoder involves the inversion of a $t \times t$ binary matrix \mathbf{L}_s with a complexity of $\mathcal{O}(t^3)$ binary operations, where $0 \leq t \leq n - k$, in comparison with the conventional OSD algorithm, which requires $\mathcal{O}(n(n - k)^2)$ operations for the Gaussian elimination [8]. This is especially helpful in reducing the pre-processing complexity of OSD algorithms, which has been a significant obstacle to efficient hardware implementation.

A. A Modified OSD Algorithm for high-rate PR Codes

We consider a binary-input additive white Gaussian noise (BI-AWGN) channel. For the transmit codeword \mathbf{c} , the modulated signal denoted by \mathbf{x} , is given by $z_i = 1 - 2c_i$ for $i = 0, \dots, n-1$. At the channel output, the i th received signal is given by $r_i = x_i + w_i$, where w_i is AWGN with zero mean and variance $N_0/2$. Similar to [3], we define the reliability of r_i as $a_i = |r_i|$, where $|\cdot|$ is the absolute operation. The set of positions of the k received symbols with the highest reliabilities, i.e., $\{i_0, \dots, i_{k-1}\}$, where $0 \leq i_0 < i_1 < \dots < i_{k-1} \leq n - 1$, is defined as the most reliable basis (MRB).

We propose a slightly modified OSD algorithm suitable for high-rate PR codes. In the proposed algorithm, the receiver does not need to permute the generator matrix (or the parity check matrix) according to sorted reliabilities. Instead, we first find the MRB and then transformation \mathbf{L}^{-1} , to be able to re-encode according to the MRB and the test error patterns (TEPs). As we are considering high-rate codes, finding the inverse of matrix \mathbf{L} reduces to finding the inverse of a significantly smaller matrix \mathbf{L}_s of size $t \times t$ and some matrix operations (refer to (18)). The detail of the proposed algorithm is presented in Algorithm 1. In Step 10 of Algorithm 1, we use a soft condition $D_{\min} \leq S_\ell$ and hard condition

Algorithm 1: Modified OSD for High-Rate PR Codes

Input: Received signal \mathbf{r} , Generator matrix \mathbf{G}_n , OSD order m , t_ℓ , and d_ℓ for $1 \leq \ell \leq m$

Output: Codeword estimate $\hat{\mathbf{c}}$

- 1 Calculate bit reliability $a_i = |r_i|$
 - 2 Perform hard-decision: $\hat{y}_i = 1 - \text{sign}(r_i)$
 - 3 Find the MRB $\{i_0, i_1, \dots, i_{k-1}\}$ such that $i_0 < i_1 < \dots < i_{k-1}$
 - 4 Find $t = \arg \max_j \{j | i_{k-j} \geq k\}$
 - 5 Find \mathbf{L}^{-1} according to (18)
 - 6 If the matrix $\mathbf{S} + \mathbf{D}^\top\mathbf{D}$ is not invertible, update the last t elements of MRB and repeat step 5
 - 7 Calculate $\mathbf{G}_1 = \mathbf{L}^{-1}\mathbf{G}_n^\top\mathbf{G}$
 - 8 Calculate $\hat{\mathbf{c}} = \hat{\mathbf{y}}_B\mathbf{G}_1$ and $D_{\min} = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} a_i |\hat{y}_i - \hat{c}_i|$
 - 9 Find t least reliable symbols $\mathbf{v} = \{a_{j_0}, a_{j_1}, \dots, a_{j_{t-1}}\}$, such that $a_{j_0} < a_{j_1} < \dots < a_{j_{t-1}}$
 - 10 **for** $\ell = 1 : m$ **do**
 - 11 $S_\ell = \sum_{t=0}^{t_\ell} a_{j_t}$
 - 12 **if** $D_{\min} \leq S_\ell$ **and** $\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} |\hat{c}_i - \hat{y}_i| \leq d_\ell$ **then**
 - 13 **break**
 - 14 **else**
 - 15 Find set \mathcal{T}_ℓ of TEPs of size k and Hamming weight ℓ
 - 16 **for** $\mathbf{e} \in \mathcal{T}_\ell$ **do**
 - 17 Find $\mathbf{c}^{(e)} = (\hat{\mathbf{y}}_B + \mathbf{e})\mathbf{G}_1$
 - 18 Find $D^{(e)} = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} a_i |\hat{y}_i - c_i^{(e)}|$
 - 19 **if** $D^{(e)} \leq D_{\min}$ **then**
 - 20 $\hat{\mathbf{c}} = \mathbf{c}^{(e)}$
 - 21 $D_{\min} = D^{(e)}$
 - 22 **end**
 - 23 **end**
 - 24 **end**
 - 25 **end**
 - 26 Return $\hat{\mathbf{c}}$
-

$\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} |\hat{c}_i - \hat{y}_i| \leq d_\ell$ to terminate the decoding earlier and avoid testing extra TEPs.

B. Simulation Results

We first compare the block error rate (BLER) performance of PR codes and the BCH codes under the maximum likelihood (ML) decoding. As can be seen in Fig. 2, a PR code performs very close to the BCH code, particularly when the rate decreases. It is important to note that one may find a primitive polynomial for the PR code to achieve a better BLER performance than that in Fig. 2. The primitive polynomials used for constructing PR codes in this section are provided in Appendix A.

PR codes can be easily designed for any information blocklength, codeword length, and rate, and a single primitive polynomial can be used to construct codes at any rate. Fig. 3 shows the BLER performance of a PR code with $k = 59$ and a fixed primitive polynomial (Appendix A, $k = 59$) at various rates, when the proposed OSD decoder (Algorithm 1) with $m = 3$ is used.

Fig. 4 shows the BLER performance of the CA-Polar code decoded using the CA-SCL decoder with list size 16 and

TABLE I

OSD DECODING PARAMETERS WHEN $k = 234$ AND $n = 256$.

E_b/N_0 [dB]	3.38	3.88	4.38	4.88	5.38	5.88
d_1/d_2	8/9	7/8	5/6	4/5	3/4	3/4
t_1/t_2	11/11	11/11	10/10	10/10	10/10	10/10

Fig. 2. The ML performance of short high-rate BCH [14] and PR codes.

SGRAND [5]. We also show the BLER performance of a PR code decoded using the proposed modified OSD algorithm (Algorithm 1) with the maximum order of $m = 2$. As can be seen, the PR code with the proposed decoder outperforms the CA-Polar code with the CA-SCL decoder and performs very closely to the GRAND decoder.

Fig. 5 shows the average number of TEPs or codeword inquiries for the proposed OSD decoder (Algorithm 1) and the ORBGRAND decoder [6], when $k = 234$ and $n = 256$. For the proposed OSD decoder in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, when $k = 234$ and $n = 256$, the parameters t_ℓ and d_ℓ for Step 11 and 12 of Algorithm 1 are given in Table I. As can be seen in Fig. 5, the proposed OSD decoder requires a significantly lower number of TEPs compared with the ORBGRAND decoder. While the proposed algorithm requires fewer TEPs, ORBGRAND benefits from highly efficient hardware implementation, with its error pattern generator designed as a simple, efficient, and parallelizable circuit.

We note that the complexity of Algorithm 1, in terms of the number of TEPs can be significantly reduced by considering ordered TEPs [4] and sufficient and necessary conditions [3]. Moreover, Gaussian elimination, and accordingly the matrix inversion in (18), can be implemented efficiently using parallel algorithms [13], suitable for hardware implementation. These are, however, beyond the scope of this paper.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We proposed an enhanced ordered statistics decoder (OSD) tailored for decoding primitive rateless (PR) codes. Our approach simplifies the decoding process by constructing PR codes using linear Boolean functions and identifying dual bases over $\text{GF}(2^k)$ further streamlined by leveraging self-dual bases. This results in a reduced-complexity OSD algorithm. Simulation results show that high-rate PR codes perform on par with BCH codes in terms of block error rates across various SNRs and code rates. Additionally, the flexibility of PR codes, which can be customized for any rate and block length, along with the efficiency of the OSD algorithm

Fig. 4. The BLER performance of different channel coding schemes using various decoding algorithms.

Fig. 5. The average number of TEPs for the proposed OSD algorithm when decoding a PR code with $k = 234$ and $n = 256$, with parameters detailed in Table I.

requiring relatively few test error patterns, makes this solution particularly suitable for low-latency applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Shirvanimoghaddam, M. S. Mohammadi, R. Abbas, A. Minja, C. Yue, B. Matuz, G. Han, Z. Lin, W. Liu, Y. Li, S. Johnson, and B. Vucetic, "Short block-length codes for ultra-reliable low latency communications," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 57, no. 2, pp. 130–137, 2019.
- [2] C. Yue, V. Miloslavskaya, M. Shirvanimoghaddam, B. Vucetic, and Y. Li, "Efficient decoders for short block length codes in 6G URLLC," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 61, no. 4, pp. 84–90, 2023.
- [3] C. Yue, M. Shirvanimoghaddam, B. Vucetic, and Y. Li, "A revisit to ordered statistics decoding: Distance distribution and decoding rules," *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, vol. 67, no. 7, pp. 4288–4337, 2021.

- [4] C. Yue, M. Shirvanimoghaddam, G. Park, O.-S. Park, B. Vucetic, and Y. Li, "Probability-based ordered-statistics decoding for short block codes," *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 25, no. 6, pp. 1791–1795, 2021.
- [5] K. R. Duffy, M. Médard, and W. An, "Guessing random additive noise decoding with symbol reliability information (SRGRAND)," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 70, no. 1, pp. 3–18, 2021.
- [6] K. R. Duffy, W. An, and M. Médard, "Ordered reliability bits guessing random additive noise decoding," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 70, pp. 4528–4542, 2022.
- [7] M. Shirvanimoghaddam, "Primitive rateless codes," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 69, no. 10, pp. 6395–6408, 2021.
- [8] M. P. C. Fossorier and S. Lin, "Soft decision decoding of linear block codes based on ordered statistics," in *Proceedings of 1994 IEEE International Symposium on Information Theory*, Jun 1994, pp. 395–.
- [9] R. Lidl and H. Niederreiter, *Introduction to finite fields and their applications*. Cambridge university press, 1994.
- [10] S. T. J. Fenn, M. Benaïssa, and D. Taylor, "GF(2^m) multiplication and division over the dual basis," *IEEE Transactions on computers*, vol. 45, no. 3, pp. 319–327, 1996.
- [11] D. Jungnickel, A. J. Menezes, and S. A. Vanstone, "On the number of self-dual bases of GF(q^m) over GF(q)," *Proceedings of the American Mathematical Society*, vol. 109, no. 1, pp. 23–29, 1990.
- [12] F. Lázaro, G. Liva, and G. Bauch, "Inactivation decoding of LT and Raptor codes: Analysis and code design," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 65, no. 10, pp. 4114–4127, 2017.
- [13] A. Bogdanov, M. C. Mertens, C. Paar, J. Pelzl, and A. Rupp, "SMITH-A parallel hardware architecture for fast Gaussian elimination over GF(2)," in *Workshop on Special-purpose Hardware for Attacking Cryptographic Systems (SHARCS 2006), Conference Records*, 2006.
- [14] M. Helmling, S. Scholl, F. Gensheimer, T. Dietz, K. Kraft, S. Ruzika, and N. Wehn, "Database of Channel Codes and ML Simulation Results," 2019. [Online]. Available: www.uni-kl.de/channel-codes

APPENDIX A

PRIMITIVE POLYNOMIALS OF PR CODES

A given primitive polynomial $p(x) = p_0 + p_1x^2 + \dots + p_{k-1}x^{k-1} + p_kx^k$ can be represented as a binary vector $\mathbf{p} = [p_0, p_1, \dots, p_{k-1}, p_k]$. To simplify the representation, \mathbf{p} can be represented in the hexadecimal format.

The primitive polynomials for PR codes used for simulations are obtained by generating random irreducible polynomials and checking for primitivity. Our results show that a random primitive polynomial with a relatively large Hamming weight achieves near-optimal performance. The list of primitive polynomials for PR codes used in this paper is provided in Table II.

TABLE II

LIST OF PRIMITIVE POLYNOMIALS IN THE HEXADECIMAL FORMAT.

k	$p(x)$
45	2C763D3721E5
51	D34B815161EE9
57	3E307A2F28D157D
59	A35272FB2574BD3
99	92EC8E6670A47F3F2EA123837
106	794C5FD0612D7F972669F27ADC7
113	2B0656931089E30A17624C506B4FF
234	4B7A79EB6552CDB5FE30C7E135BD1AA B2D33C30299036FFE697D6DE76A7
490	6C67D752BB7A1C10B951186576B8A7FD7 775BBD406540F8FF1041D156331535950D9 7A067F30EE0DEA56E69BDEFEE86336382D D7C44B7846D2E6501BF60D
1002	6A44F26815A09D8F408D9DB34ECD7AF51 CC601F53BB10A0C99CF4C492D8AB9699E 58F57EED45A597B7B6B62BF2CDA14569 DAD6A39863A5921194D6E0BDAE6808B17 7B66D88D0F4AA9D5EB6A20F2E789C767E 94E9BDD2BA7EA53ECC40F1DA69DAD47 F89B15C0176F611A8212E0CD6DB954B68 FA7FFA5C26D1DD7BFBF8C3